

Parental Involvement in Relation to Learners' Academic Performance

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Abstract:

Parental involvement refers to the amount of participation parents have when it comes to the schooling of their children. In the Philippines, some schools foster healthy parental involvement, but sometimes parents have hesitations to involve themselves with their children's education. This study aimed to determine the level of parental involvement in relation to learners' academic performance in one of the schools of a big-sized division in Central Visayas for the School Year 2024-2025. The variables included were age, average family monthly income, highest educational attainment and number of children. The areas included were Parenting, Communicating, Volunteering, Learning at Home, Decision Making, and Collaborating with Community. The target respondents for the study were the 142 sample parents from a total population of 224, whose children are enrolled in school for School Year 2024-2025. The findings of the study showed that profile of the respondents showed a somewhat balanced distribution of respondents in terms of age, average family monthly income and highest educational attainment while there seemed to have a disparity in the number of parents who have fewer versus many children. The level of parental involvement in terms of Parenting, Communicating, Volunteering, Learning at Home, Learning at Home, and Collaborating with Community were all on high level. When grouped according to aforementioned variables, the level of parental involvement in the said areas were all on high level. The level of learners' academic performance for the 1st and 2nd quarters of School Year 2024-25 is very satisfactory. There was a significant difference in the level of parental involvement in the areas of communicating when grouped according to age; and in the area of volunteering when grouped according to average family monthly income. There was no significant relationship between parental involvement and learners' academic performance.

Keywords: Academic Performance, Decision Making, Parental Involvement

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

The External Partnerships Service (EPS) of the Department of Education (DepEd) hosted a PTA webinar in November 2021 called "Parents' Role for a Better Learning at Home," which offered parents best practices and techniques for enhancing the home learning experience for Filipino students. Regarding this, former Secretary Leonor Briones said that parents are essential to their children's development because they foster holistically developed individuals in addition to the lessons they gain from their teachers. (DepEd, 2021).

The degree to which parents participate in their children's education is referred to as parental involvement. While some Philippine schools encourage positive family involvement, parents may hesitate to get involved in their kids' education. Conversely, Western nations aggressively encourage parental involvement in their children's education and speak with parents' one-on-one to encourage them to do so (Bartolome, 2018).

In contrast to the outdated belief that parents must physically attend school in order to be involved, parents can show their involvement by reading to their children, helping them with homework or assignments, talking about school events, attending parent-teacher conferences, and/or volunteering in the classroom or during school-related events (Casey, 2022).

Involving parents is essential to ensuring consistent student achievement, but not all parents are required to or choose to engage in school activities or spend time sitting with their children to help them with their academic work. Approximately 5 to 8% of parents are either passive, indifferent, or completely uninvolved in their children's education, according to the researcher's firsthand observations as a tenured teacher in a public school. Although there are well-established studies showing that involved parents have a beneficial impact on their kids' education, the situation is different in rural locations, like the one where this researcher lectures. Many parents just leave their children's education in the hands of their teachers. This study is borne out of the researchers' motivation to determine

the impact of parental involvement in their children's education from a more localized, focus group and provide a sensible recommendation if proven otherwise.

Current State of Knowledge

Involving parents is essential for school security because it creates a safe and nurturing environment, reinforces safety procedures, and gives parents the ability to take an active role in protecting their kids and the school community. Effective implementation of safety measures depends on parents' support and adherence to safety procedures, which is increased when they are actively participating in school safety activities. The school community is strengthened by parental involvement, which fosters a sense of shared accountability for security and safety (Jordan, 2020).

Involving parents in a school's community outreach program is essential because it improves student outcomes by raising academic achievement, engagement, and social-emotional development; it also builds a supportive learning environment and promotes the school-family-community connection. The notion that education is a cooperative endeavor including families, schools, and the community is strengthened by parental involvement. It fosters a sense of collective accountability and pride in the academic achievement of students. It promotes a feeling of support and belonging by strengthening ties between parents, educators, and community members (Casey, 2024).

A lot of research has been done on how parents affect their kids' academic performance. It is commonly established that variables such as parents' educational experience and social standing can predict students' academic success, school adjustment, and parental participation. Additionally, research consistently shows that parents have a positive attitude toward their children's education when teachers ask for and expect parental involvement. This is thought to help parents see their own involvement as significant from the perspective of the teachers (Ravenelli, 2022).

However, Ravenelli (2023) argued that recently parents' roles and perceptions began to take center stage as subjects of parental involvement research, in contrast to studies that examine the role and perceptions of teachers or that analyze the attributes of both parents and teachers in relation to children's academic success. The history of school and home contexts, which established views of each other as entities with distinct and complementary objectives, can help to explain that. In the past, schooling was a school duty, and parents were solely responsible for the basic well-being and healthy development of their children. The importance of parents' attitudes and actions is increasingly being considered from a holistic point of view as these two enormous jobs increasingly merge into one another.

According to Cooper (2019), we now know that parents who feel that their own involvement has a significant impact on their child's academic success are more likely to support the growth of their child's interests than parents who do not think so. Research-identified role beliefs are partially associated with task-value, as it is known in contemporary expectancy-value theory. Task-value beliefs are important factors that influence decision-making, perseverance, and task engagement. The four elements of task-value that Eccles and Wigfield described are costs, utility value, intrinsic value, and achievement value. In terms of parental engagement, these elements would include (a) the personal significance that a parent would attach to positively influencing their child's education; (b) the authentic joy that a parent would experience from doing so; (c) the relationship that a parent would attribute between positively influencing their child's education and their own life goals; and (d) the amount of work or unpleasant experiences that a parent feels they must endure in order to do so.

Ewings (2020) compared parents who employed learning-style preference tactics with parents who employed standard homework procedures in order to investigate how parents felt about helping their elementary school children with their homework. The study also looked at elementary kids' perceptions of their academic selves and attitudes toward homework. Although many parents are unaware of the best ways to assist, teachers frequently expect parents to get engaged with their children's homework. An experimental research design was employed in this study. 68 parents and 66 students who were randomly assigned to the treatment or comparison groups participated in the study. The experimental parent group was given information on their own preferred learning style as well as that of their child. Additionally, they were trained on how to assist with homework according to the learning preferences of each child. Training on conventional homework techniques, excluding the learning-styles component, was given to the comparison group. Over the course of eight weeks, all participants used the methods for seven of those weeks. Each group kept track of and documented parent-assisted homework data on a survey created by the researcher.

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study is grounded on the two (2) formidable theories namely, Herbert J. Walberg's Theory of Performance in Education and Joyce Epstein's Theory of Parental Involvement (1980). Parental awareness and preparedness is included in the theory since it explains the relationship between parental involvement and school-family-community relationships. The notions of parental involvement in the educational process and collaboration and cooperation between the school and parents are taken into account. Furthermore, this perspective happily acknowledges the importance of parental involvement in ensuring the caliber of education that kids get. Epstein (1980) asserts that

parental involvement is critical to each child's intellectual development. He claims that if one knew the processes of family involvement that can be included in school communities, planning to ensure parent support and engagement would be easier. Schools can involve parents in a number of ways, and school communities may find it beneficial to combine the different parent participation strategies that Epstein describes. Most importantly, this approach can be used to improve students' academic performance by redefining the principles of parental involvement. Relationships between the community and the school can also be assessed using it. This is in line with an increasing body of research on the importance of family involvement in schooling. The concept of the study is based on the notion that parental involvement is crucial to each student's academic development. Second, the elements affecting learning that affect a student's academic performance are addressed by the Theory of Performance (ToP), also known as the Theory of Educational Productivity. In order to test his hypothesis, he combined his study with over 3000 papers and consulted the views of many theorists. Social-emotional factors affected eight of the eleven important domains of variables he identified in his theory: classroom management, student-teacher interactions, parental support, social-behavioral qualities, and motivational-effective features. Students' academic performance is influenced by a variety of socioeconomic factors, including the presence of a qualified teacher in the classroom, the teacher-to-student ratio, attendance, the student's sex, family income, the mother and father's educational backgrounds, and the distance between schools. Students are every educational institution's most precious asset. Students' academic success and social and economic development are closely intertwined. In order to produce the best graduates who will be the country's future workforce and leaders and eventually propel its social and economic progress, student performance is essential. Numerous studies have been conducted on the measurement of student academic performance; it is a challenging topic in academic literature, and scientific students' success is influenced by social, psychological, economic, environmental, and personal factors.

Objectives

This study aimed to determine the level of parental involvement in relation to learners' academic performance in one of the schools of a big-sized division in Central Visayas for the School Year 2024-2025. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions: 1) determine the profile of the respondents in terms of Age, Average Family Monthly Income, Highest Educational Attainment, and Number of Children; 2) determine the level of parental involvement in terms of Parenting, Communicating, Volunteering, Learning at Home, Decision-making, Collaborating with the Community; 3) determine the level of learners' academic performance for the 1st and 2nd quarters of School Year 2024-25; 4) determine if there is a significant difference in the level of parental involvement when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables; and 5) determine if there is a significant relationship between parental involvement and learners' academic performance.

Methodology:

This section presents the discussion of the research methodology used, the subjects and respondents of the study, the research instruments used, the validity and reliability of the instruments, the procedure for data gathering, and the statistical tools and procedure for data analysis.

Research Design

This study used descriptive research design to determine the level of parental involvement in relation to learners' academic performance in one of the schools of a big-sized division in Central Visayas for the School Year 2024-2025. According to Ary (2017), descriptive research involves collecting data in order to test hypotheses or to answer questions concerning the current status of the subject of the study. A descriptive study determines and reports the way things are. Descriptive research is scientific research that describes about event, phenomena or fact systematically dealing with certain area or population.

Study Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 142 parents sampled from the 224 total population in the said school. Since the population of the respondents are quite large, the researcher employed sampling technique using Cochran's Formula. The respondents were randomly selected by the researcher from each section using the lottery technique.

Instruments

To determine the level of parental involvement, this study made use of a self-made data gathering instrument which was subjected to Validity (4.82 - excellent) and Reliability testing (0.794 - acceptable). The questionnaire consisted of two parts: Part 1 gathered the respondents' socio-economic information, such as Age, Average Family Monthly Income, Highest Educational Attainment, and Number of Children. Part 2 contained a total of 30 line-items. There were 5-line items for each of the six (6) areas mentioned.

Data Gathering Procedure

After the approval of the questionnaire by the panel members, the researcher sought the help of three experts for the validation of the instrument, and subsequently conducted a reliability test as mentioned earlier. The researcher also submitted a request to the School's Division Superintendent, through the office of the Public School's District Supervisor, asking permission to conduct the study. After the approval, the researcher proceeded with the reliability test. In order to collect the data, written communications asking permission to conduct the study was sent to the Schools Division Superintendent. The purpose of the letter was to provide the SDO and the SDS a proper heads-up as to the purpose of the study, when and how the study will be conducted. The data gathering instrument was administered after the approval was secured and the copies of the instrument were retrieved after 3 days. After the collection of data, they were organized for statistical interpretation.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 used Descriptive Analytical scheme and the statistical tools used were: Frequency Count and Percentage Distribution to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of Age, Average Family Monthly Income, Highest Educational Attainment, and Number of Children.

Objective No. 2 used Descriptive Analytical scheme and the statistical tools used was Mean to determine the level of parental involvement in terms of Parenting, Communicating, Volunteering, Learning at Home, Decision-making, Collaborating with the Community.

Objective No. 3 also used Descriptive Analytical scheme and the statistical tools used was Mean to determine the level of learners' academic performance for the 1st and 2nd quarters of School Year 2024-25.

Objective No. 4 used Comparative Analytical Scheme and the statistical tool used was Mann-Whitney U Test to determine if there was a significant difference in the level of parental involvement when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 5 used Relational Analytical Scheme and the statistical tool used was Spearman Rho to determine if there is a significant relationship between parental involvement and learners' academic performance.

Ethical Consideration

In the conduct of this study, key ethical principles guiding the use of human participants and minors were strictly observed. These included providing the teachers, parents, and students with the necessary information to make a determination as to whether they want to be part of the study. The signing of the consent form, which is actually a process rather than an event was not used as coercive tool to compel participants to complete the study. They were assured of their right to withdraw from the study at any point when they became uncomfortable with the study. The identity of the children as well as their responses was kept confidential such that neither the responses nor their identity was revealed to any other person outside the research team.

Results and Discussion:

This section deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data gathered to carry out the objectives of this study. All these were made possible by following certain appropriate procedures so as to give the exact data and solution to each specific problem.

Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age, Average Family Monthly Income, Highest Educational Attainment and Number of Children

Table 1
Profile of Respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Age	Younger (Below 35 years old)	76	53.52
	Older (35 years old and above)	66	46.48
	Total	142	100.00
	Lower (Less than P13 000)	79	55.63

Average Family Monthly Income	Higher (P13 000 and above)	63	44.37
	Total	142	100.00
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower (Elementary Graduate)	66	46.48
	Higher (High School and College Graduate)	76	53.52
	Total	142	100.00
Number of Children	Few (Less than 2 children)	51	35.92
	Many (2 or more children)	91	64.08
	Total	142	100.00

Table 1 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of age, average family monthly income, highest educational attainment and number of children. It can be seen in the results that the number of younger respondents (below 35 years old) with 76 respondents or 53.52% is slightly higher than the older respondents (35 years old and above) with 66 respondents of 46.48%. There were 79 respondents or 55.63% who belong to the lower income bracket (less than P13,000) and 63 respondents or 44.37% who belong to the higher income group (P13,000 and above). There were 66 parents or 46.48% who at least completed or reached elementary education and 76 or 53.52% of them reached or completed either high school or higher education. As to their number of children, 51 respondents or 35.92% have less than 2 children; while 91 or 64.08% have more than 2 children in their families. The profile of the respondents showed a somewhat balanced distribution of respondents in terms of age, average family monthly income and highest educational attainment while there seemed to have a disparity in the number of parents who have fewer versus many children.

Level of parental involvement in terms of the following areas of Parenting, Communicating, Volunteering, Learning at Home, Decision Making, and Collaborating with Community

Table 2
Level of Parental Involvement in the Area of Parenting

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a parent, I ...		
1. make sure that my children are physically safe at home.	3.87	High Level
2. provide the needs of my children.	4.25	High Level
3. provide a conducive learning space for my child at home.	4.13	High Level
4. teach my child how to manage his/her time effectively.	3.68	High Level
5. provide a conducive learning space for my child at home.	3.97	High Level
Overall Mean	3.98	High Level

Table 2 reveals the level of parental involvement in the area of parenting with a mean score of 3.98, interpreted as "high level". This means that most of the parents are personally involved in facilitating the education of their children. The highest mean score was recorded for item no. 2 which states that "As a parent, I provide the needs of my children" with a mean score of 4.25, interpreted as "high level" while item no. 4 which states that "As a parent, I teach my child how to manage his/her time effectively" got the lowest mean score of 3.68, interpreted as "high level". This result shows that some parents have issues in personally coaching their children how to manage personal and free time so as to effectively use them in studying. This limitation could be attributed to the constraint of time among parents who are currently employed or those who are meager time connecting with their children for coaching purposes. This quantitative study result of Zamora (2022) on parental awareness in the implementation of self-learning modules provided parallel support to this finding. The study's line item which states that "As a parent, I give ample time to guide my child" got the lowest mean score of 3.46, interpreted as moderate level" and that result was equally attributed to the fact that many parents lack quality time to spend with their children as they were employed.

Table 3
Level of Parental Involvement in the Area of Communicating

Items	Mean	Interpretation
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1. always communicate with the teacher on a regular basis.	4.25	High Level
2. regularly ask about school activities to know where I can support.	4.12	High Level
3. discuss school concerns and issues personally with my child.	3.61	High Level
4. talk to my children regarding school matters.	4.09	High Level
5. assist school projects and assignments.	3.99	High Level
Overall Mean	4.01	High Level

Table 3 reveals that parental involvement in terms of communicating was on high level with a mean score of 4.01. This means that the parents are indeed engaged with their children's education particularly in speaking with their teachers in school. Line-item No. 1 which states that "As a parent, I always communicate with the teacher on a regular basis" with the highest mean score of 4.25, interpreted as "high level" while Item No. 3 which states that "As a parent, I discuss school concerns and issues personally with my child" got the lowest mean score of 3.61, interpreted as "high level". This means that despite their higher engagement with the teachers, there are parents who may have missed out talking personally to teachers about the individual progress and concerns of their children in school. This result runs parallel with the results of Binaloga (2022) who conducted a study on parental involvement during the pandemic. Aline item stating "As a parent I ask the teacher as to what areas is my child needing support" got the lowest mean score in that study indicating that some parents are less involved in communicating with the teachers of their children, purposely, to know the strength and weaknesses of the child in his academic life'.

Table 4
Level of parental involvement in the area of Volunteering

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. take lead roles in children's outdoor activities.	4.22	High Level
2. provide support in all school activities.	4.02	High Level
3. help organize fundraising activities.	3.53	High Level
4. lend utensils and wares for children's campout.	3.91	High Level
5. partake in school undertakings where parents support is needed.	3.93	High Level
Overall Mean	3.92	High Level

Table 4 reveals that parental involvement in terms of volunteering is on high level with a mean score of 3.92, indicative of the fact that parents are generally up to their feet doing voluntary works for their children's school. Item No. 1 which states that "As a parent, I take lead roles in children's outdoor activities" got the highest mean score of 4.22, interpreted as "high level" while Item No. 4 which states that "As a parent, I lend utensils and wares for children's campout" got the lowest mean score of 3.91, interpreted as "high level". Volunteerism comes in various forms and this happens to be the least of them. Parents indicated here that some of them are unable to lend, specifically, some kitchen utensils for the children's campout. This can be attributed to the non-availability of said extra utensils or some parents are not just available at the time when said utensils are needed by the children. Cooper (2019) said that we know that parents who believe that their own role is important in affecting their child's achievement in school tend to more often facilitate the development of their child's interests, in comparison to parents who do not view their role as important. Role beliefs identified in research are, in part, related to what modern expectancy-value theory refers as task-value. Task-value beliefs are key determinants of choice, persistence, and engagement in tasks. Eccles and Wigfield outlined four components of task-value: attainment value, intrinsic value, utility value, and costs. Regarding parental engagement, these components would refer to (a) the personal importance the parent would attribute for positively contributing to their child's learning; (b) the genuine enjoyment the parent would feel about doing so; (c) the relation the parent attributes between positively contributing to their children's learning and their own personal goals in life; and (d) the amount of effort or negative experiences a parent feels they have to go through in order to do so.

Table 5
Level of Parental Involvement in the Area of Learning at Home

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. read with my children at home.	3.95	High Level
2. purchase books and other reading materials for my children.	4.27	High Level

3. make sure that my children are free from disturbance during study time.	4.16	High Level
4. provide enough lighting for my child's study area.	3.97	High Level
5. have internet connected at home for my child's research purposes.	3.85	High Level
Overall Mean	4.04	High Level

Table 5 reveals the high level of parental involvement in terms of learning at home with a mean score of 4.04, interpreted as "high level". This shows that parents are highly involved and engaged in making sure that learning at home is given proper attention. The line item which says "As a parent, I purchase books and other reading materials for my children" got the highest mean score of 4.27, interpreted as high level while the line item which says "As a parent, I have internet connected at home for my child's research purposes" got the lowest mean score of 3.85, interpreted as "high level". The utilization of internet connection at home is needed especially when blended learning is being implemented, however, not everyone has the capacity to pay for its monthly dues. Added to the fact that there are areas where internet connection is not really available due to topography. Technology has been deeply rooted in education for more than two decades, however, technological revolution through portable gadgets such as mobile phones has brought changes radically. Mobile phones have changed the way students seek knowledge and develop cognition. Thus, learning through mobile technology, facilitated by access to academic resources, socializing with each within and outside the physical boundaries and sharing experiences, helps to back the learning objectives of individuals as well as institutions (Farid, Ahmad, Niaz, Arif, Shamshirband, & Khattak, 2015).

Table 6
Level of Parental Involvement in the Area of Decision Making

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. provide sensible suggestions during school meetings.	3.82	High Level
2. take part in discussing school security issues.	3.38	Moderate Level
3. adhere to collegial decision-making style.	3.94	High Level
4. help other parents by presenting the pros and cons of an issue.	4.12	High Level
5. consult teachers and my child always before throwing-in any decision.	3.66	High Level
Overall Mean	3.78	High Level

Table 6 reveals that parental involvement in terms of decision making is high at a mean score of 3.78, this is indicative of the fact that parents are assertive of their rights when it comes to key decision-making in the learning process of their children. Item No. 4 which states that "As a parent, I help other parents by presenting the pros and cons of an issue" got the highest mean score of 4.12, interpreted as "high level" while Item No. 2 which states that "As a parent, I take part in discussing school security issues" got the lowest mean score of 3.38, interpreted as "moderate level". This indicates the leniency of some parents in participating in the discussion, and in the decision-making process of the school with the stakeholders on how to secure the school and provide blanket security to learners and teachers. Often in the literature, studies of parental involvement are focused on involvement at home (home-based involvement, meaning parents' behavior towards school life and practicing activities related to school learning with their children at home, such as parents helping their children with homework, parents discussing schooling with their children, parental monitoring of school tasks and rule-setting), involvement with the school (school-based involvement related to parents' various forms of participation in the schools' activities), or acknowledge both places for the analysis of involvement behaviors and activities (home-school communication, such as parents interacting with teachers). Some studies also establish a difference between school-initiated parental involvement and parent-initiated involvement.

Table 7
Level of Parental Involvement in the Area of Collaborating with Community

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. work with other parents in fulfilling classroom needs.	4.22	High Level

2. join school community outreach programs.	3.38	Moderate Level
3. contribute some amount to help extension programs.	3.63	High Level
4. share suggestions with community leaders on how to keep our children safer.	4.06	High Level
5. openly share or exchange ideas with others on community meetings.	3.94	High Level
Overall Mean	3.85	High Level

Table 7 shows that parental involvement in terms of collaborating with the community is on high level with a mean score of 3.86. This implies that parents, generally, are actively participating with the school's program in rendering community outreach programs, or in partaking in all other undertakings that seeks to help the community. Item No. 1 which states that "As a parent, I work with other parents in fulfilling classroom needs" got the highest mean score of 4.22, interpreted as "high level" while Item No. 3 which states that "As a parent, I join school community outreach programs" got the lowest mean score of 3.38, interpreted as "moderate level". This implies that there are some parents who are unable to participate in the school's community outreach program which is understandable particularly for parents who are employed or those who are located in far-flung areas. Communication is also a key factor in this result.

The study of Lartec (2021) explored the collaborative perspective of teachers and parents for materials development in a multilingual setting. Respondents were six parents and six teachers from two of the pilot schools of Mother tongue based multilingual education in a melting pot city of different languages and cultures. The research design employed was qualitative to gain insights, explore the depth, richness and complexity inherent in the social or cultural phenomenon. Data were gathered from interviews with the aid of audio recorder and interview guide based on Malone (2007).

The Level of Learners' Academic Performance for the 1st and 2nd Quarters of School Year 2024-2025

Table 8

Level of Learners' Academic Performance for the 1st and 2nd Quarters of School Year 2024-2025

Variable	Mean	Interpretation
Academic Performance	86.42	Very Satisfactory

Table 8 shows the academic performance of the learners for the first two (2) quarters of School Year 2024-2025. The average mean was 86.42, interpreted as "very satisfactory". This indicates that with whatever the parents are currently doing to assist their children, it is already good and helpful. With most of the results in high level, it reaffirms earlier notions that indeed, when parents are involved, learners tend to perform better as they feel supported and well-assisted. However, the result shows that there is a vast potential for improvement. With deeper parental involvement, this general average can be potentially improved into "outstanding" level. Parental involvement directly translates to improved academic performance, with students from involved families showing higher grades, better test scores, and increased motivation, along with improved school attendance and behavior. Studies consistently demonstrate that students with involved parents tend to achieve higher grades and test scores. Parental support and encouragement can foster a love of learning and increase a student's motivation and engagement in their studies (Casey, 2022).

Comparative analysis in the Level of parental involvement in the areas of Parenting, Communicating, Volunteering, Learning at Home, Decision Making, and Collaborating with Community when grouped and compared according to variables Age, Average Family Monthly Income, Highest Educational Attainment and Number of Children

Table 9

Difference in the Level of Parental Involvement in the Area of Parenting when Grouped and Compared According to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	76	65.93	2085.000	0.076	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	66	77.91				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	79	73.23	2351.500	0.564		Not Significant
	Higher	63	69.33				

Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	66	73.64	2367.000	0.554	Not Significant
	Higher	76	69.64			
Number of Children	Few	51	74.33	2176.000	0.528	Not Significant
	Many	91	69.91			

Table 9 reveals that there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement when grouped according to age, average family monthly income, highest educational attainment and number of children. The p-values are 0.076 for age, 0.564 for average family monthly income, 0.554 for highest educational attainment and 0.528 for number of children, all these values are above the 0.05 significant level, leading towards the acceptance of the hypothesis that states “there is no significant difference in the level of parental engagement” in terms of parenting. This indicates the fact that when parents are doing their parental duties, age, income bracket, education or number of children has no effect on such duties. The way parents carry out this type of personal obligation. Rudolfa (2019) said that for several years now, the literature has emphasized the relevance of different variables in mediating the level of parental involvement, from parental/family characteristics to student variables, and school characteristics. Some examples of parental/family variables that are associated with parental involvement include: sociodemographic factors (e.g., more education seems to relate to higher levels of involvement at school; being a father or mother has mixed results in the literature—some studies show non-significant influence of students’ level of education, others mention that mothers show higher levels of involvement; parents’ perceptions of their child’s academic competency and need for their support (perception of lower learning autonomy usually increases the frequency of parents’ involvement); and parents’ time to support (having more work demands or family responsibilities, such as more children, is negatively associated with involvement).

Table 10
Difference in the Level of Parental Involvement in the Area of Communicating when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	76	64.70	1991.000	0.032	0.05	Significant
	Older	66	79.33				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	79	69.90	2362.000	0.599	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	63	73.51				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	66	74.64	2301.000	0.391	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	76	68.78				
Number of Children	Few	51	73.60	2213.500	0.645	0.05	Not Significant
	Many	91	70.32				

Table 10 shows that there is a significant difference in the level of parental involvement when grouped according to age, in the area of communicating. The p-value is 0.032 which is less than the 0.05 significant level, therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected in this category. On one hand, there was no significant difference when grouped according to average family monthly income, highest educational attainment and number of children in the same area. The p-values are 0.599, 0.391, and 0.645, respectively, all are above the 0.05 level of significance, thus in these 3 variables the null hypothesis is hereby accepted. This implies that in terms of communication age is a key factor. Older respondents believed that it is important for them, as parents, to communicate with the teacher, with fellow parents and to their children as well. Having a strong belief on the role of communication in parenting is really very important, indeed. The study of Ewings (2020) examined parent attitudes when assisting with elementary school students’ homework, comparing parents who used learning-style preference strategies with parents who used traditional homework strategies. The study also examined the attitudes toward homework and the academic self-perception of elementary students. Teachers often expect parents to become involved in their child’s homework, but many parents are unsure of the strategies to use when helping. This study used an experimental research design. Participating in the study were 68 parents and 66 students randomly assigned to either the treatment or comparison group. The experimental parent group received data on their own learning style and their child’s learning-style preferences. They also received training on strategies to help with homework based on each child’s learning-style preferences. The comparison group received training on traditional homework strategies without the learning- styles component. All participants implemented the strategies for seven weeks of an eight-week period. Each group monitored and recorded information about parent-assisted homework on a researcher-designed survey.

Table 11

Difference in the Level of parental involvement in the area of Volunteering when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	76	66.41	2121.500	0.105		Not Significant
	Older	66	77.36				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	79	64.97	1972.500	0.030	0.05	Significant
	Higher	63	79.69				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	66	69.15	2353.000	0.515		Not Significant
	Higher	76	73.54				
Number of Children	Few	51	71.68	2311.500	0.969		Not Significant
	Many	91	71.40				

Table 11 reveals that there is a significant difference in the level of parental involvement in volunteering when grouped according to average family monthly income. It has a *p*-value of 0.030, less than the 0.05 significant level, thus the null hypothesis is accepted for this variable. There was no significant difference when grouped according to age, highest educational attainment and the number of children. The *p* values are 0.105 for age, 0.515 for educational attainment and 0.969 for number of children, all these values are more than the 0.05 significant level, which means that the null hypothesis is rejected. This indicates that income significantly affects abilities of parents to volunteer in some school projects and activities. Volunteering is easier for the higher income parents and relatively not okay for the lower income group. This is understandable because parents who have lesser financial capacity who always choose to work 8 hours a day compared to parents who earn more. Parental volunteerism at schools, a crucial form of parental involvement, significantly benefits students, parents, teachers, and the school community by enhancing student achievement, behavior, and overall school environment, while also fostering stronger parent-teacher relationships. Volunteering provides opportunities for parents and teachers to interact and build relationships, leading to better communication and collaboration (Diaz, 2020).

Table 12

Difference in the level of parental involvement in the area of Learning at Home when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	76	64.51	1977.000	0.029		Significant
	Older	66	79.55				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	79	72.63	2399.500	0.713	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	63	70.09				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	66	73.65	2366.000	0.558		Not Significant
	Higher	76	69.63				
Number of Children	Few	51	72.99	2244.500	0.745		Not Significant
	Many	91	70.66				

Shown on Table 12 is the level of parental involvement in terms of learning at home and it shows here that there is a significant difference when grouped according to Age. The *p*-value is 0.029, this is below the 0.05 significant level, thus the null hypothesis is rejected. When grouped according to average family income, highest educational attainment and number of children, there was no significant difference. The *p*-values are 0.713 for monthly income, 0.558 for education and 0.745 for number of children, all these are higher than the 0.05 significant level, therefore the null hypothesis is accepted. This implies that age affects the way parents carry out their duties in provide a better learning home environment. Based on the result, older parents tend to be more attentive to students' learning at home, teaching them at times, and providing a clean and well-ventilated study space. Older parents have been through this with other children while this experience may be the first for the younger parents. Parental involvement in home learning encompasses activities like helping with homework, creating a supportive learning environment, and communicating with teachers, all aimed at fostering a child's academic success. Assisting children with their assignments, ensuring they understand the material, and providing

a structured learning environment. Establishing routines, setting aside dedicated study time, ensuring access to resources, and creating a positive and encouraging atmosphere (Gan, 2019).

Table 13
Difference in the level of parental involvement in the area of Decision Making when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	76	73.61	2347.500	0.499	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	66	69.07				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	79	71.29	2472.000	0.944	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	63	71.76				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	66	74.78	2291.500	0.361	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	76	68.65				
Number of Children	Few	51	72.57	2266.000	0.811	0.05	Not Significant
	Many	91	70.90				

Table 13 shows that there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement in terms of decision making with the p-values showing as 0.499 for age, 0.944 for family income, 0.361 for educational attainment and 0.811 for number of children. All these values are above the 0.05 significant level therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. This clearly implies that age, income, education and the number of children have no impact on parents' decision to get involved in decision making. They share the same sentiment over its importance in children's education. Parental involvement in school decision-making strengthens the education process, improves academic outcomes, and fosters a positive school environment, benefiting students, parents, and teachers alike. Being involved in school decision-making can foster a stronger partnership between parents and educators, leading to better communication and collaboration. Parental involvement allows parents to better understand their child's emotional and intellectual needs, as well as their strengths and weaknesses (Durisic, 2018).

Table 14
Difference in the Level of Parental Involvement in the Area of Collaborating with Community when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	76	68.87	2308.000	0.406	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	66	74.53				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	79	70.85	2437.500	0.831	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	63	72.31				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	66	70.64	2451.000	0.813	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	76	72.25				
Number of Children	Few	51	68.40	2162.500	0.495	0.05	Not Significant
	Many	91	73.24				

Table 14 reveals that there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement in terms of collaborating with the community when grouped according to age, average family income, educational attainment and number of children. The p-values are 0.406, 0.831, 0.813 and 0.495, respectively, all values greater than the 0.05 significant level, therefore the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that in terms of collaborating with the community, age, average income, education and number of children have no influence on parents. They have a shared opinion that collaborating with the community is just as important with other activities. Parental involvement in collaborating with the community is crucial for a supportive learning environment, as it reinforces the idea that education is a collaborative effort between schools, families, and communities, leading to better student outcomes. Engaged families often gain access to a network of resources and support provided by the school and community, including information on nutrition programs, healthcare services, and educational workshops (Eden, 2024).

Relational analysis between the level of parental involvement and the level of learners’ academic performance

Table 15

Relationship between the level of parental involvement and the level of learners’ academic performance

Variable	Rho	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Level of Parental Involvement	-0.125	0.139	0.05	Not Significant
Learner's Academic Performance				

Table 15 reveals that there is no significant relationship between parental involvement and learners’ academic performance. The p-value is 0.139, greater than the 0.05 significant level, therefore the hypothesis that states “there is no significant relationship between parental involvement and academic performance is hereby accepted. This provides us an information on the independence of learners where with or without parental involvement in their education, they will be able to perform well in school. This result is contrary to the findings of Jaiswal (2019) who conducted a paper review the research literatures on the relationship among parenting practices such as parenting style, parents' expectations, parental home and school involvement activities and students' academic performance with the focus on elementary and middle school level. The reviews of empirical researches indicate that different constructs of parental involvement play an important role in various ways. Several studies however indicate a decline in parental involvement during the middle or above school levels. Furthermore, the review indicates that authoritative parenting style is positively associated academic performance across all school level, although this finding is not consistent across ethnicity, culture and socioeconomic status. Parental home based and school-based involvements have also been positively related to academic performance with some inconsistency. One the other hand parental expectations for their child educational attainment have the strongest impact on academic performance compared with other types of parental involvement constructs such as participation in school events, parent-child communication, and help in homework.

Conclusions:

The study presented a balanced opinion considering the distribution of respondents as indicated by the percentage distribution, except for their educational attainment. However, the overall distribution indicated non-bias in the opinion of the respondents. The parental involvement is on high level across the six (6) areas considering the fact that parents are indeed hands-on with their children’s education. This also shows that majority of the parents understand the need for them to provide the needs of their children, communicate with teachers and other parents, participate in school activities and serve as volunteers at times, including helping the school with community outreach activities. Most parents understand that all these activities are essential to make them effective as parents. Regardless of their variable groupings, the high level of parental involvement indicates that the parents have a shared opinion on parenting, communicating, volunteering, learning at home, decision making and collaborating with the community. The academic achievement of learners which is at a ‘very satisfactory level’ indicates that despite some limitations and challenges, they are able to perform well. However, there is still a bigger room for improvement as they can potentially land the “outstanding” level. The significant difference in the areas of communicating and volunteering when grouped according to age and income level are indicative of the fact that older respondents are way conversant than the younger ones and they are able to talk to teachers or their children easily, as compared with the younger parents. On the other hand, volunteering takes one’s physical presence thus the lower income bracket is less likely to be present because they need to prioritize their employment to sustain a living. The absence of any significant relationship shows that learners can perform well in school, with or without their parent’s involvement. This is indicative of the independent learning skills of the learners, because they can indeed have good academic results on their own.

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References:

Alicamen, D. and Abadiano, . (2020). *Parents as Study Buddy in the New Normal of Teaching: A Grounded Theory. Journal of Psychology and Education*. Vol. 57, No. 9. Pp. 5434 -5447.

- Anoba, J. and Cahapy, M. (2020). *The Readiness of Teachers on Blended Learning Transition For Post-Covid-19 Period: An Assessment Using Parallel Mixed Method*. *International Journal of Teaching, Education and Learning*. Vol. 4, No. 2.
- Bartolome, M.T. (2018). *Parental Involvement in the Philippines: A Review of Related Literatures*. *International Journal of Early Childhood Education Care*. 6 (1): 41-50.
- Casey, A. (2022). *Parental Involvement in Your Child's Education: The Key to Student Success, Research Shows*. The Annie E. Casey Foundation.
- Castroverde, F. and Alcala, M. (2021). *Modular distance learning modality: Challenges of teachers in teaching amid the Covid-19 pandemic*. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*. 10 (8)
- Dayagbil, F. (2021). *Teaching and Learning Continuity Amid and Beyond the Pandemic*. *Frontiers of Education*.
- Garcia, E. and Weiss, E. (2020). *COVID-19 and student performance, equity, and U.S. education policy*. *Economic Policy Institute*.
- Gonser, S. (2020). *3 Ways to Deepen Student Engagement in Online Discussions: Blended Learning*. George Lucas Educational Foundation.
- Kariyev, A. et al. (2017). *A study of teacher's readiness for teaching students by methods of interactive learning as a condition for developing students' creative abilities*.
- Kondakciu, Klaudia. (2020). *Technology's Impact on Education - The Philippines*. https://yourshumanly.org/technologys-impact-education-philippines/?gclid=CjwKCAiA4veMBhAMEiwAU4XRrwlvrjMLgb7vjn8Rm36_oXqOFw8bAfL_babo1rHdZpg-gqmLG-cIoBoCQI8QAvD_BwE
- Lase, D. et al. (2020). *Parents' Perceptions of Distance Learning during Covid-19 Pandemic in Rural Indonesia*.
- Lapada, A. et al. (2020). *Teachers' Covid-19 Awareness, Distance Learning Education Experiences and Perceptions towards Institutional Readiness and Challenges*. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*. 19 (6): 127-144
- Li, C. and Lalami, F. (2020). *The COVID-19 pandemic has changed education forever*. *The World Economic Forum*.
- Mahdy, M. (2020). *The Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic on the Academic Performance of Veterinary Medical Students*. *Frontiers of Veterinary Science*. Department of Anatomy and Embryology, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, South Valley University, Qena, Egypt.
- Olivo, M. (2021). *Parents' Perception on Printed Modular Distance Learning in Canarem Elementary School: Basis for Proposed Action Plan*. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research Articles*. (2) 4.
- Ozudogru, G. (2020). *Problems faced in distance education during Covid-19 Pandemic*. *Participatory Educational Research*. University of Turkey. 8 (4): 321 - 333.
- Ravanelli, D, et al. (2020). *Teacher's Readiness Level in Implementing Work from Home Policy in Indonesia*. *Department of Public Administration Faculty of Administrative Science, University of Indonesia*.
- Ribeiro, L. et al. (2021). *Parental Involvement during Pandemic Times: Challenges and Opportunities*. *Educ. Sci*. 2021, 11, 302. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci11060302>
- Tria, J. (2020). *The COVID-19 Pandemic through the Lens of Education in the Philippines: The New Normal*. *Journal of Pedagogical Development and Lifelong Learning*. 1 (1).
- Utami, A. (2022). *The Role of Parental Involvement in Student Academic Outcomes*. *Journal of Education Review Provision*. 2 (1): 17-21.